

A Study on the Current Status of Lab-Grown Meat Commercialization in India

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ABSTRACT

Meat lovers want to consume more meat whereas vegans are not preferring to eat meat and are against the idea of slaughtering animals. Climate change and various natural phenomena affect the climate over the regions so that it directly or indirectly affects agriculture. Due to this, there would be food security concerns. So, vegans can't access all kinds of foods which rich in protein and vitamins. To safeguard the interest of vegans and prevent the slaughtering of animals, we could utilize lab-grown meat. Non-vegans prefer meat because utilizing meat for consumption would meet all the essential proteins. Promoting lab-grown meat could solve both problems and helps in maintaining the ecological balance. The only concern associated with lab-grown meat is the taste and then less satisfying for meat eaters because it's hard for them to go through this transition. Cultured meat is healthy but people showing hesitant to consume it. This research provides the opportunity to promote lab-grown meat over conventional meat. This study also aims to find out people's perceptions regarding cultured meat by conducting a survey in a particular location and assessing the population's perspective regarding consuming lab-grown meat. This research goal is to showcase why people prefer conventional meat and to find out vegan's interest to prefer cultured meat. In the social context of India due to its diversified culture, people have different perspectives in terms of food and this research paper address the differential needs of all people regarding meat consumption.

Keywords: Lab-grown meat; Tissue culture; Commercialization; Consumer food behavior; Social context; Meat alternatives.

I. INTRODUCTION

Meat is rich in many nutrients like proteins, essential amino acids, vitamins, and minerals, including vitamin A, iron, or zinc, which account for the world's biggest deficiency of nutrients. Currently, the population is increasing, and a rise in economic growth can also be seen. (Yongli *et al.*, 2022) From the beginning, there are so many ethical issues and concerns associated with the consumption of meat. Many don't eat because they think that animals go through torture physically and mentally. There are so many animal welfares also to protect animals against their torture and slaughtering. The world population is expected to reach 9 billion by the year 2050 (Daniel., *et al* 2019).

Since manufacturing meat requires a lot more energy than creating other foods, the current techniques of producing meat may not be able to keep up with the rising demand for meat as a result of rapid population growth. The consumption of meat has long been criticized for harming the environment and people's health. The negative impacts of meat-eating on the environment and public health have long been criticized (Daniel., *et al* 2019). Many studies on the production of meat substitutes are being conducted to guarantee the security and sustainability of the food supply chain. The closest product to meat on the market right now is plant-based meat, which is made from materials like grains, soybeans, wheat, etc. Meat produced in a laboratory, commonly referred to as cultivated or cultured meat, is made from the animal cells themselves (Christina Charmpi *et al*, 2021). The creation of lab-based meat has been used to replace items produced by animal slaughter with a more hygienic and contamination-free process. Given that the technology allows for the modification of the amino acid and lipid profiles as well as the enrichment of vitamins, minerals, and bioactive substances, cultured meat has the potential to become an excellent functional meal that meets the unique dietary requirements of people with various illnesses. Also, the risk of zoonotic disease transmission from animals to humans and foodborne illness may be greatly decreased by meat produced in laboratories under sterile, strictly controlled conditions without the use of antibiotics. However, as lab-based meat has a much greater potential for protecting the environment than traditional meat, including cutting greenhouse gas emissions and reducing environmental pollution, eating it is better for the environment than eating conventional meat (Charmpi *et al*, 2021). Moreover, less land and water are used, both of which are necessary for animal growth. (Ching *et al.*, 2022).

There has been a lot of interest in the production of cultured meat from animal cells in vitro ever since the first cultured meat hamburger was presented in 2013. Some businesses with long-term strategic goals have switched their focus from developing healthy meat production and delivery networks as a method of generating cultured meat, away from optimizing the traditional meat production process. As a result, there is a sizable market for meat substitutes. Currently, Just Food, Beyond Meats, Impossible Foods, and Mosa Meat, are the world's leading lab-based meat and fish producers (**Ching et al., 2022**). By 2027, it was estimated that the market for meat substitutes would be worth \$4 billion.

II. Production of cultured meat

The tissue culture method is used to make cultured meat, also referred to as cultured meat. Dutch scientist Mark Post created the first cultured meat in 2013 when he made the world's first cultured meat hamburger patty (**Bhat et al., 2015**). The selection of an appropriate cell line, which can come from either an animal cell source or a pluripotent cell source, is the first stage in the synthesis of cultured meat. This can be done in two ways, the first is biopsy-based by taking a specific cell type which can be muscle cells or any organ cells of the target animal (chicken). The second method involves using pluripotent cell sources such as animal-induced pluripotent stem cells or embryonic stem cells. After extracting the cells of interest, they are subjected to a bioreactor where the cells are mixed along with the media which contains growth factors, and various amino acids important for growth (**Reiss et al., 2021**).

The muscle-resident progenitor cells from the animal body are directly extracted from the skeletal muscle of chicken, in the case of pluripotent stem cells they are allowed to differentiate into three germ layers, particularly the mesodermal cell lineage. Once the progenitor cells have multiplied to an adequate level in the bioreactor, they can terminally grow into mature cells and tissues as cultured meat. To give the finished meat its shape and cellular organization, the created flesh is permitted to go through scaffolding. This method will make the meat flavor and feel similar to traditional meat. The final cultured meat must also undergo various quality assurance to ensure the best possible quality with proper shelf-life (**Siddiqui et al., 2022**).

2.1 Target market

According to a report from Statista, China is the largest meat consumer in the world followed by the United States of America. The growing meat consumption in the world is directly linked to the gross domestic product, as developed countries are associated with larger meat consumption than developing and underdeveloped countries (**Whitton C et al., 2021**). As the population is skyrocketing people are consuming more and more meat products across the world. In India, nearly 70% of the population consumes some form of meat and according to a Statista report, In India, approximately half of the population eats non-vegetarian food once a week. Among all forms of meat, the consumption of chicken predominates at 3.2 kg/per capita **OECD (2023)**, Meat consumption (indicator) due to its availability. So cultured chicken can be the perfect substitute for conventional meat (**Kamalapuram et al., 2021**). India has recently become the world's most populous country, and as a result, the need for meat is increasing daily, leading to the mass murder of animals to meet this demand. Thus, our target market will be the common meat-consuming people. According to statistical data collected by India Today, the East and South-East part of India consumes more meat than the rest of India and among all the states, the state of Kerela is the largest consumer of meat. Hence, the primary target of our cultured meat is these parts of India, and once the product gets the proper recognition, we will market our product in other parts of the country.

2.2 Financing of cultivated meat products

Investors from around the world have become very interested in cell-based cultured meat due to the prospective market opportunities. (**Choudhury et al., 2020**). The growing population in India is demanding more food to meet their required nutrition level. According to **OECD (2023)**, the annual poultry meat consumption of India is only 3.2 kilograms per capita compared to 68.7 in Israel and when compared to animal meat India stands very low compared to other major countries. Despite this low meat consumption rate, the livestock sector contributed 4.11% to the GDP of India for the year 2022 (Department of Animal Husbandry and Dairying). Due to this, there is much research going through the country, there are startups like clear meat which manufactures cultured meat, particularly chicken, and they promised to produce their product in bulk within the next 2 years. Many countries like the USA, China, Singapore, and Israel had already allotted a major fund for research in this sector. A bill authorizing the sale of cultured beef products on the Singaporean market was already passed by the Singaporean government at the same time (**Young Lee et al., 2022**).

III. Materials and methods

3.1 Study design

This research was carried out online with Google Forms. We distributed the questionnaire to one hundred randomized participants, and the confidentiality of the results was maintained, and none of the results were shared with others. The study consisted of ten well-designed questions to assess the consumer's attitudes toward consuming lab-grown meat. The obtained results were assessed thoroughly in an unbiased manner to get insights into their idea towards commercializing lab-grown meat in India, and their acceptance rate was also analyzed.

IV. RESULTS

To ascertain how consumers would react to or accept artificially produced meat, and its products, we designed a set of questionnaires and distributed it to people through google forms. From our study reports, we discovered that (70%) of the responses are in the 20–30 age range, while most of them are college students. Among the total number of respondents, (61.7%) of our them were females, while (36.7%) of them were males. In the first question, we asked our respondents whether they consider themselves vegetarian or non-vegetarian, among the total number of respondents, (75%) of the people consider themselves non-vegetarian and consume some form of meat, and only (25%) of them were vegetarian. This shows the growing demand for meat consumption among people, particularly young and middle-aged people.

In the next question, we asked the meat-consuming people about their frequency in the consumption of meat per week. where we found that (40%) of people consume some form of meat twice or three a week, while (30%) of people consume once a week. This data pretty much resembles the data published by the OECD (2023), where the results showed that Indian people consume meat only once per week. On the following question, we asked our respondents about the form of meat they consume the most, we found that (65%) of our respondents consume chicken the most, followed by mutton (16.7%) by interpreting this result we can understand that, lab-grown chicken meat can be the perfect replacement of conventional chicken due to high demand among consumers.

Imagine that lab-grown meat has become widely available at grocery stores, restaurants, butchers, and markets.
How likely are you to try clean meat?

Figure 1: Pie chart showing the interest of people in trying the lab-grown meat

In the next set of questions, we asked the people about the term “clean meat” or lab-grown meat to assess their familiarity with this term among people. We found that the familiarity of this term is pretty high among people, where (42.6%) of the respondents were familiar with the term, and (41%) of them haven’t heard of the term, while (16.4%) were unsure about the term. After this question, we introduced the term “clean meat” to our respondents and further asked about their concern about the acceptance of laboratory-produced meat in their food supply. We found that (33.3%) of the respondents stayed neutral and didn’t answer the question, while (25%) of the people were somewhat likely, and (15%) of them extremely likely to purchase lab-grown meat and its products. At the same time, (13.3%) of the respondents were extremely unlikely to purchase lab-grown meat and its products. Following this question, we asked our respondents about their choice of meat if they were grown in the lab for which, the majority (60%) of them chose chicken and its products, (and 18.3%), (and 5%) chose mutton and beef respectively. There were also (20%) of the respondents who chose to stick with conventionally produced meat by slaughtering animals. Apart from that, there were some (16.7%) of the people who were unsure and thus selected none of these.

In the final question, we asked the respondents to assume that they had the opportunity to experience lab-grown meat and that it tasted just like normal meat, had the same texture, and offered better nutritional value. After that, we quizzed them on a few topics, such as their likelihood of frequently purchasing lab-grown meat if the aforementioned statement were true. We found that half of the respondents (25%) were somewhat likely to purchase the meat, and the same number of people were unsure about that. While some were very unlikely to purchase lab-grown meat. After that, we questioned the respondents if they would consume meat produced in laboratories instead of traditional meat, this question was meant for the people who quit meat from their food chain due to their love for animals and against animal cruelty. This trend is increasing day by day as more people now are shifting to a vegan lifestyle due to the guilt of consuming animal meat. We found an interesting result for this question, as (27%) of them were somewhat likely, and (3%) of them were exceedingly likely to substitute lab-grown meat for traditional meat, while (6%), and (4%) of them were somewhat unlikely and extremely unlikely to replace conventional meat. Also, there were (20%) of the respondents were unsure about choosing or resisting lab-grown meat. After all these questions, at last, we asked our respondents to tell whether they will consume lab-grown meat if it rolls out to commercial production we found, most of the people (21%) were unsure about it, and may or may not shift to lab-grown meat in the future if it comes to market. Some people are ready to change and shift to lab-grown meat, While, some people chose not to shift to lab-grown meat and rely on conventional meat for their consumption.

Imagine that you have the opportunity to try lab-grown meat, and you found the taste and texture was the same as conventional meat. How likely are you to;

Figure 2 Histogram showing the acceptance of people in consuming or purchasing lab-grown meat.

4.1 Marketing strategy

According to our survey, most consumers prefer non-vegetarian over vegetarian. The figures illustrate that it is difficult to promote lab-based meat among vegetarians and it is quite easy to promote it among vegetarians (Marshall *et al.*, 2022). We could promote lab-based meat based on price adjustments because most Indians prefer essentials over luxury (Francis & Sarangi, 2022). So, we must lower the price and promote it among the educated minds of Indians in turn, this helps in making consumers who do not know lab-based meat would prefer it because they find trust in terms of consumption. Still, more Indians live in rural than in urban (Deb & Okulicz-Kozaryn, 2023). While promoting lab-based meat much in urban it may spread in rural too. Due to rapid urbanization, the rural population for employment preferring cities. So, providing plant-based meat at a low cost makes their routine sustainable and helps him/her financially stable due to its low cost with enriched nutrients. In turn, he would market in terms of suggesting plant-based meat to this rural part of his neighbors and his friends. By providing at a lower cost and meeting the nutrient need, govt may introduce this lab-based meat as part of their mid-day meal scheme (Kaur, 2021). Therefore, the key to promotion is the low cost and quality of plant-based meat. In this way, we could lower the amount of animal slaughtering (Benningstad & Kunst, 2020).

4.2 Ethical Issues

Even though cultured meat can able to address ethical and environmental concerns, many people are concerned about food safety, mostly because they believe that cultured meat is man-made. In vitro, meat raises unstoppable ethical questions, just like any other new technology. One of the main aims of this innovation, according to proponents of cultured meat, is to stop the horrific and terrible treatment of animals who are occasionally imprisoned in cramped spaces and brutally slain (Ching *et al.*, 2022). As with any new technology, in vitro, meat will have its detractors. We examine three potential objections carefully: Three ways exist in which in vitro meat tramples on both animal and natural rights: 1) It will result in a less contented animal population; 2) Cannibalism will be encouraged; and 3). In vitro, meat disrespects either nature or animals.

Cultured meat aims to use much fewer animals than conventional livestock operations. Indeed, some vegetarians, vegans, and moral omnivores who desire to reduce their meat consumption may find this appealing from the perspective of animal welfare (Hwang *et al.*, 2021). The notion presented above would be more accurate if, as some start-ups have claimed, a new type of media has been generated without the use of FBS from dead calves (Eliska *et al.*, 2018). Some vegans have avoided using animal products because of the way they taste (Christina Charmpi *et al.*, 2021). More people could consider eating it if it were raised in a humane and cruelty-free environment. The legitimacy of eating lab-produced meat has been a hot topic of debate since the product was first introduced. Some animals' meat is off-limits to eat for a variety of religious reasons, such as those relating to a healthy diet, food safety (such as the Islamic concept of Tayyib, which emphasized a clean and pure food process), ethics (such as the Jewish concept of Shechita slaughter, which aimed to minimize animal suffering), and protection of sacred animals. Islamic Shari'a law establishes the rules for when certain foods, particularly fanged carnivores, are permissible and not permissible to eat.

Among the animals that are prohibited by Jewish law known as kosher are the pig, hare, hyrax, and camel (Hwang *et al.*, 2021). Most Buddhist, Hindu, and Jain traditions consider cows or other livestock to be sacred animals. Hindus have the highest levels of approval for lab-produced meat, except cultured beef, which is universally approved by the populace. According to a survey, the majority of religions are amenable to the concept of laboratory-generated meat as long as it is made following their meat-eating habits and manufactured legitimately. (Eliska *et al.*, 2018).

4.3 DISCUSSION

The views of consumers and ethical dilemmas, which may also serve as a barrier, are key to determining whether lab-grown meat will be accepted by consumers and will be profitable. Although this is currently difficult to achieve, the product should share as many sensory and organoleptic features (taste, texture, and appearance) as naturally occurring meat, which is largely favored by customers. The complexity of the tissue-production process will be determined by how well muscle biology can be reproduced (Eliska *et al.*, 2018). To advance toward commercial-scale cultured meat production, technological and procedural advancements will need to solve issues that call for investments and partnerships. For the creation of cultured meat, problems are presented by the anticipated demand and the intensity of the production process (Charmpi *et al.*, 2021). But, if future technology guaranteed lab-produced meat would be healthier and have better ingredients, vegetarians and vegans might be convinced to incorporate it in their diets (e.g., no saturated fats, no cholesterol, is free of heme-iron, and has all the necessary vitamins and other nutrients) (Sexton, 2016). Even if no injury or violation of an animal's inherent rights were done during the meat's production, this would still be the case. Even though attempts to reduce animal-sourced foods, especially conventional meat products, are aimed at meat eaters due to these items' negative effects on the environment, human health, and animal welfare, meat eaters do not support reducing their meat intake (Charmpi *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, it has been noted that substantial obstacles to eliminating these items include the sensory characteristics of regular beef and its perceived nutritional value. This study looked at how meat eaters and vegetarians felt about using cultured meat and plant-based meat substitutes in place of traditional meat. Lab-grown meat appears to be a particularly exciting alternative to conventional meat from animal carcasses, which has difficulties with its production techniques and falls short of fulfilling expanding worldwide demands for protein supply (Eliska *et al.*, 2018).

V. CONCLUSION

With the expansion of the cultured meat industry, there will be a wider range of meat options. The commoditization of such products may, in part, relieve the pressure on the traditional animal husbandry industry. The development of highly proliferative, multipotent livestock cell sources is a substantial technical challenge in the effort to increase the production of cultured meat for commercial sale. The optimal options for the succeeding production phases, such as the composition of the culture medium, the design of the bioreactor, and the tissue scaffolding, are also determined by the proliferative capacity and differentiation potential of the chosen cell source. Recent years have seen significant advancements in the techniques used to produce pluripotent and main adult stem cell sources from livestock species. Additionally, it is a functional food that has the potential to serve the particular needs of a diverse range of consumer groups due to the adaptability of the manufacturing process and the capacity to change its composition. It is still in its infancy, though, because no technique for mass production has yet been developed. Questions, particularly moral ones, remain unaddressed. By transitioning from cattle to cultured meat, we may all gain from it: people, animals, and the environment. Cultured meat might have a superior nutritional makeup because of the highly regulated bioprocess. Cultured beef products can also help to solve the issue of many regions of the world lacking access to high-quality protein meals. Furthermore, cultured meat provides a disease-free replacement that reduces contact with animals and, subsequently, the danger of spreading zoonotic diseases.

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